

Performance of CN705-18 in multilocal trials in India, 1985-87.^a

Site ^b	Grain yield ^c (t/ha)		Max water depth (cm)
	CN705-18	Local check	
<i>Preliminary Variety Trial 5, 1985</i>			
Bhubaneswar	2.1*	1.0 (Khajuniachar)	na
CRR I	3.6*	1.2 (CR1030)	40
Patna	2.5	2.7 (Janki)	na
Chinsurah	3.3*	1.8 (NC492)	55
<i>Uniform Variety Trial 5, 1986</i>			
Chinsurah	3.3*	1.2 (TCA212)	110
Malda	3.6	3.2 (CN540)	62
Pusa	1.2	1.8 (TCA214)	85
Ranital	2.2	1.7 (CR1030)	65
<i>Physiology screening</i>			
Cuttack	4.7*	3.4 (CR1018)	50
Patna	3.2*	2.2 (Janki)	50
<i>Uniform Variety Trial 5, 1987</i>			
CRR I	3.5*	1.9 (na)	75
Bhubaneswar	2.1	2.0 (Rambha)	50
North Lakhimpur	2.9	2.9 (Panikekau)	108
Chinsurah	3.4	2.9 (NC492)	85
Pulla	2.0*	1.1 (CN540)	75
<i>Physiology screening</i>			
Chinsurah	4.0	4.0 (Jogen)	65
Maruteru	2.0*	0.7 (Marutan)	50
Mean (17 sites)	2.9	2.1	

^ana = data not available. ^bCRR I = Central Rice Research Institute. ^c* = significant at the 5% level of probability.

tolerance, elongation ability, kneeing ability, and drought tolerance at the early vegetative stage. Panicles are about 24 cm long with good exertion and about 215 grains/panicle. Grain is medium and bold (length-5.9 mm, breadth-2.9 mm, L/B 2.0), 1,000-grain weight is 27.3 g. It has a yellow-colored hull at maturity, red kernel, and strong (3 mo) seed dormancy.

On average, CN705-18 outyielded check varieties (2.9 t/ha to 2.1 t/ha) over 17 sites (see table), with an overall yield increase of 38%. CN705-18 yield was significantly higher than check at 9 sites, superior at 4, equal at 2, and lower at 2. Yield varied from 4.7 to 1.2 t/ha. This variation under similar water depths over sites reflects the role of time, duration, and intensity of water stagnation in determining variety adaptability.

CN705-18 has been recommended for large-scale demonstration trials in farmers' fields. □

SiPi 692033: a promising rainfed lowland rice variety

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SiPi 692033 (introduced from Taiwan), seven FAROX rice lines (Table 1), and FARO 27 (a widely cultivated rice variety) were evaluated at six sites across the country in 1986. Sites 1, 2, and 3 lie within the rain forest and sites 4, 5, and 6 lie in the Sudan savanna vegetational zones.

All cultural operations except weed control were common to all locations. Grain yield (14% moisture) was taken from the middle 6 m² of each test plot.

SiPi 692033 was the highest yielder overall and at five sites. Its yield advantage ranged from 18% over FAROX 228-3-1-1 to 65% over FAROX 239-2-1-1.

In general, grain yields were higher at the Sudan savanna sites with low annual rainfall (<1,000 mm) than at the rain forest sites with high annual rainfall

Table 1. Yield of rice lines and varieties in multilocation trials in Nigeria, 1986.^a

Line or variety	Parentage	Grain yield (t/ha)						Mean
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
FAROX 228-3-1-1	FARO 15/IR28	1.1	5.4	4.4	6.1	8.2	8.2	5.6
FAROX 228-4-1-1	FARO 15/IR28	1.3	5.7	5.0	5.1	7.8	7.1	5.3
FAROX 239-3-3-2	IR28/FARO 12	1.0	4.8	6.4	6.5	5.7	7.6	5.3
FAROX 233-7-1-2	FARO 12/IR28	1.3	3.9	4.5	5.8	4.6	6.9	4.5
FAROX 239-2-1-1	IR28/FARO 12	1.0	3.3	3.6	5.5	4.1	6.4	4.0
FAROX 233-1-1-1	FARO 12/IR28	1.1	5.5	5.9	5.7	5.2	7.0	5.1
FAROX 234-3-1-1	FARO 12/TOS103	1.5	4.5	5.7	7.0	6.0	6.8	5.3
SiPi 692033	SiPi 661044/ SiPi 651020	1.5	5.9	5.9	8.9	8.3	8.8	6.6
FARO 27 (check)	-	1.3	5.2	5.0	6.9	3.6	7.2	4.9
Mean		1.2	4.9	5.2	6.4	5.9	7.3	

^aLocations: 1 = Ogoja, 2 = Ibadan, 3 = Bende, 4 = Wurno, 5 = Birnin-Kebbi, 6 = Kadawa.

Table 2. Agronomic characteristics of rice lines and varieties.^a Nigeria, 1986.

Line or variety	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Maturity (d)	Grain type ^b
FAROX 228-3-1-1	110	335	117	MB
FAROX 228-4-1-1	106	311	114	MB
FAROX 239-3-3-2	109	362	114	MB
FAROX 233-7-1-2	97	356	110	LS
FAROX 239-2-1-1	78	362	108	LS
FAROX 233-1-1-1	108	379	115	LS
FAROX 234-3-1-1	94	371	119	LS
SiPi 692033	106	339	122	LS
FARO 27 (check)	95	355	120	MB

^a Mean of 6 sites. ^b LS = long slender, MB = medium bold.

(>1,500 mm). Rice in the savanna ripens under higher solar radiation.

Panicles/m² were similar for all varieties tested (Table 2). All varieties

were semidwarf (110 cm).

Both SiPi 692033 and FARO 27 have high amylose content (>25%) with hard

gel consistency (26-35 mm). SiPi 692033 has long, slender grains and higher yield than FARO 27. □

Seed technology

Influence of *Acrocyndrium oryzae* Sawada on rice seed germination and seedling vigor

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We studied the influence of *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams and D. Hawksw. (syn. *Acrocyndrium oryzae* Sawada) on seed germination and seedling vigor of seven rice varieties. Seeds were thoroughly washed with sterile distilled water and 10 seeds were later on moistened filter paper in a petri dish, with 10 replications. The

Influence of *Acrocyndrium oryzae* on seed germination and rice seedling vigor. Tamil Nadu, India, 1988.

Cultivar	Seed germination (%)		Seedling vigor ^a							
	Healthy	Inoculated	Shoot length (mm)				Root length (mm)			
			Day 4		Day 7		Day 4		Day 7	
			NI	I	NI	I	NI	I	NI	I
IET9233	95	93	15.3	10.7	32.4	29.1	14.6	13.9	32.2	29.1
ET8611	89	84	6.6	4.8	19.1	18.7	16.2	14.8	33.0	31.3
IET8584	96	92	5.3	3.6	25.9	25.2	15.0	13.2	30.4	30.3
IR62	90	87	4.8	3.6	15.4	7.8	12.0	10.3	29.6	27.2
AU1	90	86	10.5	7.3	26.1	23.1	20.3	17.2	59.9	47.2
J58	92	89	7.6	6.3	33.5	24.7	15.7	13.6	41.8	40.4
ADT37	94	91	4.3	3.6	9.7	1.9	16.8	15.6	44.0	39.3
LSD (P = 0.05)	4.34		2.35				3.42			

^a NI = not inoculated, I = inoculated.

seeds were sprayed with a 4×10^6 spores/ml suspension of the fungus. (Control seeds were sprayed with sterile distilled water.) Seed germination and seedling vigor were assessed 4 and 7 d

after inoculation.

Inoculation considerably reduced seed germination in all varieties (see table). Shoot and root lengths of all the rices also were reduced. □

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Boiling water treatment to improve germination of *Sesbania rostrata*

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The hard seed coat in *Sesbania rostrata* can be broken by treating seeds with concentrated sulfuric acid for 40 min. However, sulfuric acid is costly and requires care. Dormancy due to hard seed coat in many legumes could be

Germination of *S. rostrata* seeds treated with boiling water (98 °C). Dharwad, India, 1988.

Treatment	Germination (%) at indicated period after treatment				
	3 d	4 d	5 d	6 d	7 d
Control (no boiling water)	2	4	4	4	4
Treatment with 98 °C water					
15 s	34	40	50	62	62
30 s	42	52	54	70	70
45 s	42	52	60	72	76
60 s	52	66	66	74	76
75 s	42	60	66	78	78
90 s	54	62	62	70	72 (4) ^a
120 s	64	76	76	76	76 (8)
150 s	50	60	60	60	60 (10)
180 s	50	68	68	68	68 (10)

^a Figures in parentheses = percent deformed seeds.